

Spotlight

Mitochondrial Venus is more likely to have a lower birthweight

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Assisted reproductive technologies (ART) are associated with a moderately higher risk of preterm birth and low birthweight, but the causes are unknown. A recent study by Mertens *et al.* reveals a link between being born through ART, ovarian stimulation, and an increased incidence of mitochondrial heteroplasmic variants that correlate with lower birthweight.

Sandro Botticelli's painting 'The Birth of Venus' beautifully depicts a mythological scene of a child conceived *ex utero* from the severed genitals of the God Uranus that were thrown into the sea. As such, Venus can be considered to be the first child conceived by assisted reproduction in Western culture. The myth became reality in 1978 when the first child was born following *in vitro* fertilization (IVF). By now the number of IVF births has reached 12 million. Although this innovation is a great blessing for subfertile couples, it is still not clear how and to what extent the use of ART might affect the health of progeny.

Follow-up studies of ART children have not revealed any drastic or severe consequences for health. Nonetheless, modest increases in the risk of some complications have been observed. The highest recognized risks associated with ART are preterm birth and low birthweight – for both conditions ART increases the relative risk by 1.8-fold in comparison to spontaneous conception (SC) which in absolute

terms increases the risk from 7% to 12% [1]. Although these results were obtained by adjusting for known confounding factors, in the absence of an actual mechanistic insight into causality, the observed risks cannot be attributed solely to the use of ART. Depending on the cause of infertility, the magnitude of the ART manipulations differs between patients, making the subfertile patient group very heterogeneous. Furthermore, neither hormonal treatment protocols nor the *in vitro* culture conditions of IVF embryos are standardized. The available data indicate that different embryo culture conditions do not have a significant impact on preterm birth and birthweight [2], whereas the use of ovarian stimulation (OS) might [3]. However, it is not known whether the detrimental effect of OS is due to the quality of the oocytes or to the impact of hormonal stimulation on the uterus [4]. Therefore, clear mechanisms for how ART affects the health of the offspring still need to be unraveled.

The IVF procedure augments chromosomal instability in early embryogenesis, but this was not found in IVF neonates [5]. It is plausible that defects that ultimately increase aneuploidies and mosaicism in IVF embryos also cause changes in mitochondrial DNA (mtDNA) with unknown persistence. Our mtDNA seed is established during embryonal development when the primordial germ cells (PGS) form. PGS have approximately ten mitochondria, representing a tiny fraction of the initial oocyte mitochondrial pool of ~100 000 that was fertilized and developed into the gastrulating embryo with PGS at 2–3 weeks. This genetic bottleneck can cause an accumulation of mutated mtDNA variants in the oocyte pool, resulting in a state of heteroplasmy – meaning that a fraction of the mtDNA pool inside a cell is mutated – and this increases the risk that a less frequent mtDNA variant in the mother will become dominant in the oocyte [6]. Later in life, different stressors and particularly age-

related changes in women increase oxidative damage to proteins and lipids that are associated with the accumulation of *de novo* mtDNA heteroplasmy in oocytes and also increase the possible mitochondrial health-associated risks in children [6–8]. Depending on the pathogenicity of the mutation, heteroplasmy needs to reach a particular level for a disease to develop. A higher mitochondrial mutation load in the placenta has been linked to preterm birth and newborn sex-specific changes in birthweight, and a higher mutational load has been associated with lower and higher birthweight among females and males, respectively [9].

An elegant study by Mertens *et al.* attempted to clarify whether, apart from aging, ART also increases variants in mtDNA which translate into low birthweight associated with ART [10]. The authors first assessed a cohort of 270 ART and 181 SC individuals with similar birthweight. They found no differences in heteroplasmy frequency between the two groups: among both the SC and ART groups more than half of the individuals had heteroplasmy, and carried up to five divergent mtDNA variants. As the mean load of heteroplasmy per region of mtDNA did not differ, the authors used statistical methods to reduce the complexity of the data, and they found that ART individuals more frequently have heteroplasmy in the protein-coding and/or rRNA gene regions, with fewer mutations in other regions. To estimate the frequency of germline *de novo* mutations the authors also analyzed the mtDNA of 67 ART and 90 SC mother–child pairs. Interestingly, they found that ART children had a higher load of heteroplasmy for *de novo* non-synonymous protein-coding variants. There are several possible causes of the more frequent mtDNA mutations seen in ART-conceived individuals, including (i) the germline of the mothers of ART children could be subjected to more stressors, (ii) *in vitro* ART conditions, and (iii) the ART procedure may affect the

uterine milieu during early pregnancy. All these mechanisms could lead to *de novo* heteroplasmy in oocytes and embryos or increase the load of already existing oocyte-derived heteroplasmy.

To test whether OS in ART could affect the *de novo* rate of mtDNA mutagenesis, the authors compared oocytes retrieved from natural cycles and those from OS of the same women and their somatic mtDNA. They found that maternal age correlated more strongly with the total load of *de novo* mtDNA variants and rRNA variants,

whereas the numbers of oocytes retrieved from OS correlated positively with the increase in *de novo* non-synonymous and rRNA variants. One possible explanation for this phenomenon could be that OS disrupts the natural competition for follicle-stimulating hormone among the developing follicle–oocyte complexes, and the absence of competition might enable the ovulation of oocytes containing mtDNA heteroplasmy.

In addition, the authors found that the aforementioned mtDNA variants associate with

lower birthweight in SC individuals and a subgroup of ART individuals. However, this association was not seen in ART individuals alone. The results were obtained by combined analysis of SC individuals and a subgroup of ART individuals. This sub-study excluded children conceived through ART that utilized the now obsolete embryo culture medium, that had a dominant effect on the birthweight of children.

Taken together (Figure 1), Mertens *et al.* provide proof that some mtDNA variants are associated with lower birthweight in SC children and that these mtDNA variants are more frequent in ART children and in oocytes from ovarian stimulation procedures with higher oocyte yield. In combination with age-related changes, ovarian stimulation could be another stressor that influences oocyte quality. The seminal results presented by Mertens *et al.* could form the basis of larger cohort studies to determine whether this in fact causes the higher incidence of low birthweight in ART babies.

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Author contributions

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Declaration of interests

The authors declare no conflicts of interests.

Figure 1. Aging and ovarian stimulation increase mitochondrial DNA (mtDNA) mutations that are associated with lower birthweight. (A) The oocyte mitochondrial pool is established in early embryogenesis via a bottleneck and is subjected to environmental stressors throughout life. The frequency of mutated mtDNA increases as women age naturally and during ovarian stimulation with higher oocyte yields. (B) Individuals conceived with assisted reproductive technology (ART) more frequently have heteroplasmy for non-synonymous protein-coding and rRNA gene variants, and these are associated with lower birthweight in spontaneously and ART-conceived individuals. Figure created with BioRender.

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